

Two New Sterols from a Sea Pen of *Virgularia* species of Indian Coast

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The ethyl acetate extract of a sea pen of *Virgularia* species furnished two new sterols-24-methylcholesta-16,20(22)-dien-3 β -ol and 24-methylcholesta-17(20),22-dien-3 β -ol.

In continuation of our work on the bioactive secondary metabolites from marine flora and fauna of Indian seas¹, we report herein the isolation of two new sterols from a sea pen of *Virgularia* species (phylum: Coelenterata) collected off Laccadives coast of the Indian ocean. The structures of the sterols have been established as 24-methylcholesta-16, 20(22)-dien-3 β -ol and 24-methylcholesta-17(20), 22-dien-3 β -ol on the basis of their analytical and spectral data.

The initial methanolic extract of the animals (10 kg) was concentrated to leave an almost aqueous residue (2 dm³) which was extracted with ethyl acetate. The residue from the ethyl acetate extract on column chromatography over silica gel furnished two crystalline compounds: compound-A (200 mg) from the benzene eluate and compound-B (50 mg) from benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluate

Compound-A, colourless needles from methanol, m.p. 140–42°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 3.66^\circ$ (CHCl₃, c. 1.31), C₂₈H₄₆O, M⁺ 398, gave a positive LB test for steroids. Its ir spectrum showed a hydroxy group (3 500 cm⁻¹). On acetylation with Ac₂O and pyridine it gave a monoacetate, m.p. 146–48°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 11.17^\circ$ (CHCl₃, c. 0.51), C₃₀H₄₈O₂; ν_{\max} 1 720 cm⁻¹ (OCOCH₃); δ 1.9 (–OCOCH₃). Its uv absorption at 237.3 nm is accounted for a heteroannular diene system. Its ¹H nmr spectrum exhibited two olefinic protons as broad multiplets at δ 4.75 and 5.35 and a methyl on double bond at δ 1.70 with other signals at δ 3.5 (br m, 3 α -a-H, W₃ 16 Hz), 0.77 and 1.02 (s, C₁₈ and C₁₉ methyls), 0.88 (d, J 6 Hz, isopropyl), 0.97 (d, J 6 Hz, 24-methyl), 1.2–1.5 (20H, m) and 1.9–2.2 (4H, m, two allylic methylenes). The presence of a heteroannular diene excluded the possibility of the usual 5,6-double bond. The possible positions for the heteroannular diene system are 7,9(11), 7,14 and 8,14 of which the last could be excluded since it contains only one olefinic proton. The olefinic protons of the ring system as present in the first two systems in general appeared around δ 5.30 (Ref. 2). Both these possibilities might also be excluded as one of the olefinic protons in compound-A appeared at δ 4.75, a value which has been recorded

for an olefinic proton in the side-chain. The two other possibilities for the conjugated diene system are 16,20(22) and 20(22),23 of which the latter could be excluded since it requires two methyls on double bond. The structure of compound-A might thus be regarded as 24-methylcholesta-16,20(22)-dien-3 β -ol. This structure was also supported by its mass fragments 380 (M⁺-H₂O), 295 (M⁺-H₂O-C₆H₁₃), 254 (M⁺-H₂O-C₉H₁₇) along with the characteristic ions a (326), b (286), c (272), d (232) and e (164) of steroid fragmentation³ (Fig. 1). The structure lent further support when compound-A on refluxing with methanolic sulphuric acid was found to give an isomeric heteroannular diene (λ_{\max} 241.2 nm, m.p. 146–48°) which exhibited both the olefinic protons at the same value δ 5.30 suggesting the structure of the rearranged isomeric diene as 24-methylcholesta-15,17(20)-dien-3 β -ol.

Fig. 1

Compound-B, colourless needles from methanol, m.p. 190–92°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 45.58^\circ$ (CHCl₃, c. 1.80), C₂₈H₄₆O, M⁺ 398, gave a positive LB test for steroids. It was found to be isomeric with the compound-A by showing the presence of a hydroxy group in its ir spectrum at 3 500 cm⁻¹ and a conjugated diene from its uv absorption at 241.7 nm. It gave on acetylation a monoacetate, C₃₀H₄₈O₂; ν_{\max} 1 720 cm⁻¹ (OCOCH₃); δ 1.85 (–OCOCH₃), m.p. 142–44°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 73.21^\circ$ (CHCl₃, c. 0.57). It showed significant difference to compound-A with respect to the chemical shift of the two olefinic protons, both of which appearing at δ 4.75 in contrast to the different

signals noticed in compound-A. The rest of the spectrum resemble closely with that of compound-A showing the signals at δ 3.35 (br m, $W_{\frac{1}{2}}$ 15 Hz, 3 α -a-H), 0.72 and 1.05 (s, C₁₈ and C₁₉ methyls), 0.87 (d, J 6 Hz, isopropyl), 0.97 (d, J 6 Hz, 24-methyl), 1.2–1.4 (21H, m), 1.65 (s, 20-methyl), 1.8–2.0 (m, allylic methylene and methine). Unlike compound-A, it did not undergo any isomerisation when refluxed with methanolic sulphuric acid leaving the obvious choice for its structure, 24-methylcholesta-17(20), 22-diene-3 β -ol. The structure of compound-B was further supported by the mass fragmentation of its acetate 380 (M^+ -AcOH), 369 (M^+ -C₅H₁₁), 343 (M^+ -C₇H₁₃) along with the characteristic ions *a* (326), *b* (272), *c* (232) and *d* (164) of steroid fragmentation³ (Fig. 2).

Fig 2

Experimental

Melting points were determined on an electric hot plate and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-408 spectrophotometer, uv spectra on a Shimadzu UV-260 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS instrument.

The marine organism *V. species* (10 kg) was washed with fresh water to remove any algal contamination and then soaked in methanol. The alcoholic extract on concentration under reduced pressure yielded an aqueous residue (2 dm³) which was extracted into ethyl acetate. On concentration, the ethyl acetate extract yielded a dark green gum (6 g) which on column chromatography over silica gel with solvents of increasing polarity from hexane through benzene to ethyl acetate yielded the following compounds.

24-Methylcholesta-16,20(22)-dien-3 β -ol (1): Compound (1) from benzene eluate came as colourless needles from methanol (200 mg), m.p. 140–42° (Found: C, 84.3; H, 11.3. C₂₈H₄₈O requires: C, 84.4; H, 11.5%); $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ -3.66° (CHCl₃, c. 1.31); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 237.3 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3500, 2950, 1450, 1380, 1280 and 1080 cm⁻¹; δ 0.77 (3H, s, C-18 methyl), 0.88 (6H, d, J 6 Hz, isopropyl), 0.97 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, 24-methyl), 1.02 (3H, s, C-19 methyl), 1.2–1.5 (20H, m), 1.70 (3H, s, 20-methyl), 1.9–2.2

(4H, m, two allylic methylenes), 3.5 (br m, $W_{\frac{1}{2}}$ 16 Hz, 3 α -a-H), 4.75 (1H, m) and 5.35 (1H, m); m/z 398 (M^+ , 5), 380 (M^+ -H₂O) (56), 326(a) (20), 295 (M^+ -H₂O-C₆H₁₂) (34), 286(b) (15), 272(c) (10), 232(d) (20), 164(e) (20), 71(25) and 43(60).

Acetylation of (1): Compound 1 (10 mg) in acetic anhydride (1 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) was kept for 24 h at room temperature. Usual work up yielded the acetate (10 mg), m.p. 146–48°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ +11.17° (CHCl₃, c. 0.51); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 238.3 nm; ν_{\max} (CHCl₃) 2950, 1720, 1450, 1370, 1270 and 1075 cm⁻¹; δ 0.76 (3H, s), 0.88 (6H, d, J 6 Hz), 0.98 (3H, d, J 6 Hz), 1.01 (3H, s), 1.2–1.5 (20H, m), 1.70 (3H, s), 1.9 (3H, s), 1.95–2.2 (4H, m), 4.3 (br m, 3 α -a-H), 4.75 (1H, m) and 5.3 (1H, m).

Isomerisation of (1). Formation of 24-methylcholesta-15,17(20)-dien-3 β -ol: Compound 1 (15 mg) was refluxed for 30 min at 70° in methanolic sulphuric acid (5% ; 2 ml), then poured into water (10 ml) and extracted with chloroform (2 × 25 ml). The chloroform extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and evaporated and the resulting solid (10 mg) was crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH (1 : 1), m.p. 146–48°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ -1.62° (CHCl₃, c. 1.10); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 241.2 nm; ν_{\max} (CHCl₃) 3500 (br), 2950, 1450, 1380, 1280 and 1080; δ 0.77 (3H, s), 0.88 (6H, d, J 6 Hz), 0.97 (3H, d, J 6 Hz), 1.02 (3H, s), 1.2–1.5 (20H, m), 1.70 (3H, s), 1.9–2.2 (4H, m), 3.5 (1H, br m, 3 α -a-H) and 5.30 (2H, m).

24-Methylcholesta-17(20),22-dien-3 β -ol (2): Compound 2 from benzene, ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluates came as colourless needles from methanol, (20 mg), m.p. 190–92° (Found: C, 84.2; H, 11.2. C₂₈H₄₈O requires: C, 84.4; H, 11.5%); $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ +45.58° (CHCl₃, c. 1.80); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 241.7 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3500, 2900, 1460, 1380, 1270 and 1080 cm⁻¹; δ 0.72 (3H, s, C-18 methyl), 0.87 (6H, d, J 6 Hz, isopropyl), 0.97 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, 24-methyl), 1.05 (3H, s, C-19 methyl), 1.65 (3H, s, 20-methyl), 1.2–1.4 (21H, m), 1.8–2.0 (3H, m, allylic methylene and methine), 3.35 (br m, $W_{\frac{1}{2}}$ 15 Hz, 3 α -a-H) and 4.75 (2H, m).

Acetylation of 2: A mixture of compound 2 (10 mg) in acetic anhydride (1 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) was kept for 24 h at room temperature. Usual work up yielded the acetate (10 mg), m.p. 142–44°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ +73.21° (CHCl₃, c. 0.57); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 242.4 nm; ν_{\max} (CHCl₃) 2950, 1720, 1460, 1380, 1275 and 1070 cm⁻¹; δ 0.73 (3H, s), 0.87 (6H, d, J 6 Hz), 0.98 (3H, d, J 6 Hz), 1.05 (3H, s), 1.65 (3H, s), 1.2–1.4 (21H, m), 1.85 (3H, s), 1.9–2.0 (3H, m), 4.35 (br m, 3 α -a-H) and 4.75 (2H, m), m/z 440 (M^+ , 10), 380 (M^+ -AcOH) (20), 369 (M^+ -C₅H₁₁) (90), 343 (M^+ -C₇H₁₃) (15), 326(a) (60), 272(b) (50), 232(c) (20), 164(d) (15), 71 (25) and 43 (60).

Isomerisation of 2: Compound 2 (10 mg) was refluxed for 30 min at 70° in methanolic sulphuric acid (5% ; 2 ml), then poured into water (10 ml) and

extracted with chloroform (2 × 25 ml). The chloroform extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and evaporated. The solid obtained was observed as the starting compound (2).

Compounds 3 (hexane-benzene, 2: 8 eluate), oil (30 mg) and 4 (hexane-benzene, 4: 6 eluate), pale yellow oil (25 mg) were found to be cyclopentanone derivatives from their available data (uv and ir). Compound 5 (hexane-benzene, 1: 1 eluate), colourless viscous oil (35 mg), was found to be a butenolide from its spectral data (uv and ir). Establishment of structure of these compounds is in progress.

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